

Impact of Selection Process on the Organizational Performance in Selected South East Nigerian Brewery Firms

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of selection process on the organizational performance in selected South East Nigerian brewery firms. The study adopted the simple linear correlation research design. The population of the study consists of the management and staff of selected brewery firms, with a total of 750. A sample size of 261 was determined using the Slovin's formula, but only a sample of 242 was employed in the study. The Cronbach Alpha statistic was used to obtain index coefficient values of 0.932, 0.825, 0.832 and 0.820 for dependent variable and independent variables respectively as the instrument reliability ratio. The dataset was first subjected to normality test for the residual term using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistic, but the result revealed that the normality assumption was not satisfied for the two independent variables; hence the introduction of parametric regression analysis technique (Theil regression) was appropriately employed. The research questions were answered with Spearman rank correlation coefficient so as to establish the relationship between the dependent and independent variables in the study. The hypotheses were tested with Theil regression technique so as to measure the "significance" of the degree of relationships existing between the dependent and independent variables. The analysis was enabled by the use of R-Studio and Minitab software packages. The study concluded that a very high positive relationship existed between employment tests and creativity of selected brewery firms in selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria, while a very high positive relationship existed between selection interview and profitability in selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria. The study recommended among others that when choosing new employees, other businesses especially breweries should use selection techniques that improve overall organizational effectiveness.

Keywords: Selection Process, Brewery, Organizational Performance, South-East Nigeria, Selection interview, Profitability, Employment Tests.

INTRODUCTION

The selection process combines recruitment and selection with job designs, performance reviews, and organizational goals. To determine which candidates should be hired, a set of precise procedures is followed (Chukwu & Igwe, 2012). Recruits apply for jobs at the start of the process, and hiring decisions mark its conclusion. The initial reception of the candidate, employment tests, the selection interview, references and background checks, the medical examination, the supervisory interview, a realistic job preview, and the hiring decision are the steps in the selection process. Tests, assessment centers, and interviews are the primary means of selection (Oyadiran & Ishaq, 2023). According to Herriot, as reported by Leopold, Harris, and Watson in 2005, there are alternative techniques to selection that are systematic and processual. She also adds that assessment centers are not a method in and of it, but rather function as a combination of several methods and operate on a multi-trait, multi-methods basis (Wairimu & Kamaara, 2018).

Conversely, the rate or extent to which an organization meets its corporate goals is referred to as organizational performance (OP). The goals of the organization determine which of the many indicators can be used to gauge

performance inside the organization. Companies should gather performance data from four viewpoints, according to Kaplan and Morton in 1992: the financial perspective, the customers' perspective, the internal company perspective, and the innovation and learning perspective (Oyadiran & Ishaq, 2023). Other indicators of organizational success, besides the one proposed by Kaplan and Norton, include creativity, profitability, productivity, competitive advantage, effectiveness, efficiency, adaptability, and quality. Nigerian organizations use a plethora of unethical methods while selecting new employees. Selection discrimination, selection prejudice, and favoritism are some examples of these immoral activities (Torlak et al., 2018). Managers are given the authority to choose, evaluate, reward, and develop employees in many organizations. Issues frequently occur when these tasks are not given enough time or when they are performed without giving careful thought to how they will affect the operation of the organization. Furthermore, the majority of managers lack sufficient training in this crucial field. Employee selection may result in hiring unqualified workers who are unable to offer their all-in order to meet organizational goals if it is not given careful consideration (Namada, 2017). According to management experts, one of the most crucial production inputs is human resources. This is mostly due to the fact that humans combine, control, and coordinate other production inputs in order to meet organizational goals. However, it is unfortunate to observe that because of "god fatherism," many organizations in Nigeria fail to choose the "right" persons for the "right" Jobs.

Because organizational goals are not clearly defined, job designs are not stated in a way that facilitates the achievement of organizational goals, job descriptions and specifications are not appropriately specified, and selection procedures may be flawed, many organizations struggle to choose the right people for the right jobs (Karia et al., 2016). For example, a lot of organizations lack standardized testing tools. Because of this, test items used to evaluate prospective employees are frequently neither valid nor dependable. Furthermore, bias may be present in the interpretation of test results. Furthermore, the questions posed, the judgments of some panel members may be biased, and the scheduling of the interviews may not be appropriate in other organizations that conduct interviews. In the end, the company will select the incorrect candidates for employment.

It's a common misconception that employing someone who doesn't fit the organization's culture or particular job description could lead to major issues. Discipline issues, arguments, absenteeism, high workforce turnover, fraud, low productivity, low profitability, subpar customer service, and stifled creativity, innovation, and learning are some of the signs of these issues. All of these could lead to subpar performance from the organization. Determining the impact of the selection process on organizational performance is relevant in light of the aforementioned scenario, particularly with regard to South Eastern Nigerian brewing companies.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. To what extent is the relationship between employment tests and creativity in selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria?
- ii. What is the extent to which selection interview affects profitability in selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in this study:

H01: Employment tests have no significant impact on creativity of selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria;

H02: There is no significant relationship between selection interview and profitability in selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Operational Conceptual Framework

According to Adom et al. (2018), a conceptual framework is a logical tool in the form of a diagram that a researcher uses to thoroughly visually illustrate the interaction between markers of the independent variables (which were examined) and the dependent variable/s. The conceptual framework diagram is used by researchers to better understand the connections between the study's predictor elements and the response variable (Grace et al., 2021). In this study, the predictor (independent) variable is selection process, which was measured in terms of employment tests and selection interview, while the response (dependent) variable is organizational performance, which was measured in terms of creativity and profitability, as shown in Fig. 1

Fig. 1: Operational Conceptual Framework Showing Selection Process and Organizational Performance in Selected Nigeria Brewery Firms in South-East Zone of Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification

An attempt was made in this study to provide operational definitions for several fundamental ideas as they were applied. The ideas are as follows: Tests of employment and interviews for selection.

Tests of Employment

Devices called employment tests are used to evaluate how well candidates match job requirements. Some are tasks that mimic work environments, while others are assessments using paper and pencil (Oyadiran & Ishaq, 2023). Tests measuring intellect, personality, aptitude, ability, and accomplishment are the main categories. When it comes to general selection an intelligence test given to a group of candidates works best especially if it has undergone adequate validation. Test results can be correlated with "norms" in a way that shows how the test-taker stacks up against the population as a whole or in a particular area (Wairimu & Kamaara, 2018).

In order to forecast a candidate's expected behaviour or job, personality tests try to evaluate the candidate's personality (Wairimu & Kamaara, 2018). Ability exams assess skills relevant to the workplace, such as linguistic, mechanical, perceptual, and numerical aptitude.

Tests of aptitude are job-specific assessments intended to forecast a person's ability to carry out duties in a particular position. They can encompass things like dexterity, mechanical aptitude, numerical ability, and clerical aptitude. Tests of attainment evaluate aptitudes or competencies that have previously been picked up via education and practice.

Interviews for Selection

The purpose of the selection interview is to assess an applicant's acceptability through a structured, in-depth discussion (Wairimu & Kamaara, 2018). The most popular method of selection is selection interviews. Their adaptability is what makes them so popular. They can be modified for management, staff, unskilled, and skilled workers. Additionally, they permit a two-way information exchange in which the candidate learns about the company and the interviewers learn about each other (Oyadiran & Ishaq, 2023).

Interviews were categorized into many forms by management experts. For example, the types of interviews that Werther and Davis in 1996 distinguished between were Behavioural interviewing, Stress interviews, mixed interviews, unstructured interviews, and structured interviews (Oyadiran & Ishaq, 2023).

According to Edenborough in 2005, there are many different types of structured interviews, ranging from basic planning tools to detailed guidelines for questions and acceptable answers (Torlak et al., 2018). Several of these types of interviews are designed to collect unambiguous proof of conduct. There are numerous ways to determine the dimensions for a structured interview. The critical incident technique, which involves questioning subject-matter experts (SMEs) about important processes, is one example of these.

Theoretical Review

Reflection and Attribution Theories of Personality, which are covered below, serve as the foundation for this investigation. Once the manager or assessor has some sort of tangible encounter with the applicants, they can utilize this information to build an opinion of them by reflecting on that experience (Chukwu & Igwe, 2012). The underlying assumption of attribution theory is that humans are inherently inclined to seek out the reasons for our own actions as well as those of others. Since Heider's 1958 study, these theorists have attempted to identify the guiding principles that determine the causes of many phenomena (Oyadiran & Ishaq, 2023). These causes can essentially be divided into three categories:

- Internally controlled causes: these occur when an individual's behavior-such as effort-is used to explain the outcome.
- Internal uncontrollable causes - where the outcome is explained in terms of the individual's own behaviour, which he or she cannot control, i.e. ability.
- External causes- where the outcome is explained in terms of something him/herself, e.g. luck, other people.

Selection is relevant to attribution theory because, throughout the course of the process, assessors will unavoidably learn details on candidates' prior work performance. The candidates might be given the chance to clarify their previous actions, in which case they will likely make claims about what they believe led to the performance. According to research by Sylvester, Anderson-Gough, Anderson, and Mohamed in 2002, interviewers form a more positive opinion of applicants who give internal-controllable attributions in response to questions concerning past unpleasant experiences (Chukwu & Igwe, 2012). Interviewers formed more negative opinions of the candidates when attributions were made that implied either internal or external uncontrollable reasons.

The issue is that research shows that our understanding of causality is frequently skewed in certain ways. The strong inclination to assign blame to the actor, or to assume an internal attribution, is known as the fundamental attribution fallacy. Particularly in Western culture, which places a great focus on personal accountability, we have a tendency to overlook contextual elements that may have influenced the action (Chukwu & Igwe, 2012).

Empirical Review

The impact of strategy alignment on organizational performance: an Ethiopian university was the subject of research by Gede and Huluka (2023). Examining the effect of strategic alignment on organizational performance was the goal of the study. To measure organizational strategic alignment, clarity in the purpose, role, and process was identified and investigated. Using explanatory and descriptive research designs, the study used a quantitative methodology. 365 employees from three Ethiopian universities were selected at random using a selection procedure, taking into account the institutions' generation of establishment. For confirmatory factor analysis and path analysis, structural equation models were employed, while descriptive statistical methods like mean and standard deviation were utilized. The study's conclusions indicated that organizational effectiveness in higher education is significantly and favourably impacted by aim, role, and process clarity. The study's conclusions also showed that organizational performance differs among the institutions under investigation according to the degree of strategic alignment's implementation. Organizational leaders were advised to describe the strategic intents of their organizations along with particular objectives, based on the study's findings. Therefore, it was suggested that governing bodies support clearly defined duties and procedures for every employee.

The effects of human resource management (HRM) practices on organizational performance were studied by Khan et al. (2023). Employees from different organizations made up the target population. Each person in this population received a standardized questionnaire that was created and distributed. Investigating HRM tactics and their impact on organizational success was the goal of the study. The opinions of workers in the field were essential in addressing the research questions. With the use of a nonprobability sampling technique, 300 respondents made up the study's sample size. The sample technique used was random sampling. The research techniques and data collecting followed ethical standards. The staff members were given the questionnaire in order to collect pertinent data for analysis. The study's goal was to add to the body of knowledge already available in the field by examining the connection between HRM practices

and organizational success. The research findings furnished organizations with valuable perspectives and suggestions to refine their HRM procedures, hence leading to better performance results.

An investigation on how human resource management (HRM) practices affected organizational performance using data from the Indian banking sector was conducted by Salman et al. (2024). A sample of 325 workers from four banks answered a survey using a convenience sampling technique. Confirmatory factor analysis was used to determine the constructs' psychometric qualities, and structural equation modelling was employed to investigate the suggested theories. The study's conclusions demonstrated that staff involvement, performance reviews, and training and development all had a favorable and substantial impact on the banks under investigation's performance. Recruitment and selection, however, had a somewhat beneficial effect. By investing in suitable human resource management methods, policymakers and decision-makers may be able to improve organizational performance with the help of the research's findings. The study had equal importance for practitioners and human resource professionals who wish to support the career growth and success of their staff members.

Gap in Literature

From empirical findings, the researcher believed that there have been studies on selection process and organizational performance in Southern region of Nigeria, but no one to the best of my knowledge was carried out using Nigerian breweries in South East of Nigeria; again, the indiscriminate use of the statistical techniques was another challenge from the past literatures. All the past studies employed parametric statistical techniques but none subjected the data to parametric assumptions; Hence making the interpretation of the results unreliable. This lacuna prompted this study in order to fill the gap.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a simple linear correlation research design. It is a design used in order to establish the linear function relationship existing between the dependent and independent variables of a study (Mbah & Udegbe, 2014). It is a quantitative method of research in which two or more quantitative variables from the same group of participants are studied so as to determine if there is a relationship or co-variation between them (Waters, 2017). Since the research dwelt on the employee recruitment, employee selection and employee career development as correlates of organizational performance, the researcher considered this design most appropriate.

Target Population

The population of the study consists of the management and staff of Nigerian Breweries Plc., with a staff strength of 228; Guinness Nigeria Plc., with a staff strength of 190; Hero Breweries Plc., with a staff strength of 256 and International Breweries Plc, Imo State Depot with a staff strength of 76. The total population for the study is therefore 750. The characteristics of the population are as follows:

Table 1: Characteristics of the Study Population

STUDY FIRMS	STAFF POPULATION
Nigerian Breweries Plc, Enugu (NBPE).	228
Guinness Nigeria Plc brewed at Dubic Breweries, Aba (GNPBA)	190
Hero Breweries Plc, Onitsha (HBPO)	256
International Breweries Plc, Imo State Depot (IBPI)	76
Total	750

Source: From the Study Firms (2024).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Sampling is the act of selecting components from the study's target population in such a way that they accurately reflect the population as a whole (Creswell, 2013). Because it is frequently impossible to interview every person of the target group, sampling is used in research. The study used Slovin's formula (Maragia & Kemboi, 2021) for calculating a sample of a finite to obtain the representative sample. The formula is given below as;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: n = Sample size

N = Population size (750)

e = Margin of error or error tolerance (0.05)

$$n = \frac{750}{1 + 750(0.05)^2} = \frac{750}{2.875} = 260.8696$$

The study followed Singh & Masuku's (2014) advice and used an error margin of 5%. With a target population of 750 employees, the sample size for the employees is 261 when the error margin is 5%.

Stratification procedures were employed to ensure subjects are drawn from the 4 targeted manufacturing firms. Proportionate sampling was employed when determining the number of employees from each firm. This was computed using Bowley's formula as shown below and the results obtained were NBPE (79), GNPBA (66), HBPO (89) and IBPI (27):

$$n_h = \frac{nN_h}{N}$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} N_h &= \text{number allotted to each stratum (firm)} \\ n &= \text{Sample size} \\ N &= \text{Population} \end{aligned}$$

Research Instruments and Reliability of Instrument

As the main tool for gathering data, the researchers created their own questionnaires (Yeasmin & Rahman, 2012). According to Kothari and Garg (2014), a questionnaire is a tool that consists of a number of questions printed or typed in a specific order on a form or set of forms and distributed to the individuals involved. The instrument was constructed using a 4-point likert scale of Very Great Extent (VGE) 4; Great Extent (GE) 3; Moderate Extent (ME) 2; and Low Extent (LE) 1. To ensure the validity of the instruments for this study, the content and face validity was adopted in ascertaining the extent to which the instrument could be said to be accurate and precise in the measurement of the variables under investigation. The instruments were administered to the group outside the study area and the scores were collated. Their responses (scores) were analyzed using Cronbach alpha which yielded an index coefficient of 0.932, 0.825, 0.832 and 0.820 for dependent variable and independent variables responses respectively. The researchers therefore considered the instrument suitable and adequate for the study.

Method of Data Analysis

The research questions were answered with Spearman rank correlation coefficient, so as to establish the relationship between the dependent and independent variables in the study. The basis for the decision for the research questions' conclusion was as follows: 0.00–0.20 = very low extent relationship, 0.21–0.40 = low extent relationship, 0.41–0.60 = moderate extent relationship, 0.61–0.80 = high extent relationship and 0.81–1.00 = very high extent relationship. Hypotheses were tested with Theil regression technique, so as to measure the "significance" of the degree of relationships existing between the dependent and independent variables. This implied that it helped to ascertain if the coefficient of the relationship is significant or not. The rejection of the null hypothesis was achieved if the calculated p-value is less than the level of significance (0.05); otherwise, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Result

The researcher retrieved two hundred and forty-two (242) copies of the distributed instrument, which represents (92.7%) return rate of the distributed instrument.

Tests for Normality Assumption for the Bivariate Regression Model

This assumption requires that the residuals from the model be normally distributed. When residuals are normally distributed, we can test a specific hypothesis about a bivariate regression model. Hence, it becomes statistically important to first examine the normality assumption before proceeding to the hypotheses. However, it should be noted that when the assumption fails, using the regression model directly leads to error in the interpretation of result. Here we tested the normality assumption based on using the dependent variable with each of the independent variables via the Anderson-Darling Statistic. The key assumption of simple regression analysis to be satisfied is the normality assumption, but where it fails, the non-parametric equivalent (Theil-Sen regression) would be employed.

Normality of Errors Assumption – Employment Tests (ET) versus Creativity (C)

The hypotheses of the Anderson-Darling test are as follows:

H₀: Errors are normally distributed

H_1 : Errors are not normally distributed

Fig. 2: Normal Probability Plot of Residual for ET & C

Source: Minitab

Since the p-value (<0.010) is less than 0.05 from Fig. 2, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that the assumption of normality distributed errors is not satisfied.

Normality of Errors Assumption – Selection Interview (SI) versus Profitability (P)

The hypotheses of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test are as follows:

- H_0 : Errors are normally distributed
- H_1 : Errors are not normally distribute

Fig. 3: Normal Probability Plot of Residual for SI & P

Source: Minitab software

Since the p-value (<0.010) is less than 0.05 from Fig. 3, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that the assumption of normality distributed errors is not satisfied.

Analysis and Results of Research Questions

Research Questions/Hypotheses One to Two

The Spearman rank correlation coefficient and the Theil regression techniques were employed to address research questions and hypotheses respectively since the normality assumption of the error term was not all satisfied, Hence, the parametric Pearson correlation coefficient and linear regression analysis were no longer valid statistical tools.

Research Question One

To what extent is the relationship between employment tests and creativity in selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria?

Table 2: Spearman's Rank Correlation Summary for ET and C

Variables	n	\bar{X}	SD	r
Employment Tests	242	9.645	3.851	0.814
Creativity	242	9.252	3.573	
Very High Relationship				

Source: R-Studio Software

Table 2 shows the result obtained in respect of research question one. The result reveals that the Spearman rank correlation coefficient is 0.814, which is very high. This implies that there is a very high relationship between employment tests and creativity of selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria.

Testing of Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Employment tests have no significant impact on creativity of selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria

Table 3: ANOVA Summary for Theil-Sen Regression of ET and C

Response: C	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-value	p-value
ET	1	1488.54	1488.54	125.087	0.000
Residuals	240	2855.58	11.90		

Source: R-Studio Software

The result in Table 3 shows that the mean squares of 1488.54 for employment tests and 11.90 for residuals, F-calculation value of 125.087 and a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This indicates statistically significant result. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that employment tests have no significant impact on creativity of selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria is rejected. Hence, the study concludes that employment tests have significant impact on creativity of selected brewery firms.

Research Question Two

What is the extent to which selection interview affects profitability in selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria?

Table 4: Spearman's Rank Correlation Summary for SI and P

Variables	n	\bar{X}	SD	r
Selection Interview	242	10.223	3.842	0.831
Profitability	242	9.876	3.312	
Very High Relationship				

Source: R-Studio Software

Table 4 shows the result obtained in respect of research question two. The result reveals that the Spearman rank correlation coefficient is 0.831, which is very high. This implies that selection interview affects profitability of selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria to a very high extent.

Testing of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between selection interview and profitability in selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria.

Table 5: ANOVA Summary for Theil-Sen Regression of SI and P

Response: P	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-value	p-value
SI	1	1769.43	1769.43	123.219	0.000
Residuals	240	3447.54	14.36		

Source: R-Studio Software

The result in Table 5 shows that the mean squares of 1769.43 for selection interview and 14.36 for residuals, F-calculation value of 123.219 and a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This indicates statistically significant result. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between selection interview and profitability in selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria is rejected. Hence, the study concludes that there is a significant relationship between selection interview and profitability.

Discussion of Findings

1. In the study, it was showed that employment tests have significant impact on creativity of selected brewery firms in selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria. Again, the result of the correlation coefficient $r = 0.814$. This indicates a strong positive relationship between the two variables. This implies that when employment tests is positive, performance of brewery firms is also positive, hence; they lead to enhancement of performance. The study's results are consistent with Chukwu and Igwe (2012) assertion that there was a substantial positive correlation between employment tests and creativity in Brewery Industry of Southern Nigeria. The results of this investigation are consistent with those of Gede and Huluka (2023), whose findings showed a strong, positive correlation between strategy alignment and organizational performance.
2. For selection interview, the results show that there is a very high positive and significant relationship between selection interview and profitability in selected brewery firms in South-East Nigeria. This implies that selection interview enhances performance of brewery firms in South-East Nigeria. The results of the present investigation align with the perspective of Chukwu and Igwe (2012), who reported a positive correlation between selection interview and profitability. The result of this investigation is also similar to that Khan et al. (2023) discovery that there was a direct correlation between human resource management (HRM) practices and organizational performance.

Conclusion

Based on the data analysis, the study came to the specific conclusion that, in the brewery industry, well-designed employment tests make it easier to choose innovative employees, and well-conducted selection interviews make it easier to choose productive staff members whose contributions boost the organization's profitability.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. When choosing new employees, other businesses especially breweries should use selection techniques that improve overall organizational effectiveness. They ought to therefore model themselves after the study's organizations;
- ii. Other companies, particularly those in the manufacturing sector, should plan their work to make it easier for employees to finish projects on time and should employ suitable hiring practices to choose staff members of the highest calibre;
- iii. Employers should follow the global trend and promote the performance of employee recruitment strategies in brewery companies; firms' performance is therefore ensured.

Suggestion for Further Research

The following research areas are suggested for further studies:

- i. A study on comparative analysis of selection process on organizational performance using Nigerian Breweries in the six geo-political zones should be examined;
- ii. Analyze the impact that selection process has on organizational performance using other indicators of selection process and organizational performance other than the ones employed in this study.

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